

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

TPS2 - a new variety for Kanyakumari

S. Kalaimani, O.R. Pillai, W. W. Manuel, and M. Subramanian, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

TPS2, a derivative of IR26/CO 40 developed at the Thiruppathisaram Rice Research Station, has been released. The semidwarf (90-95 cm) with 125 d

duration is suitable for second season (Sep-Oct) sowing. In testing at the research station and in adaptive research trials over the entire Kanyakumari district, it had 16.6-31.4% increases in grain yield and 27.6-48.8% increases in straw yield over IR20 (see table).

TPS2 is moderately resistant to brown planthopper, leafhopper, and white tip nematode. It is nonlodging and nonshattering. Grain is bold, with a 1,000-grain weight of 23.5 g. □

Characteristics of TPS2 in Kanyakumari, India, 1979-86.

Variety	Grain yield		Straw yield		Duration (d)
	t/ha	% increase	t/ha	% increase	
	<i>Station trials^a</i>				
TPS2	4.6	31.4	6.4	48.8	125
IR20	3.5	—	4.3	—	125
	<i>Adaptive research trials, 1982-83</i>				
TPS2	4.1	20.1	10.8	31.7	125
IR20	3.4	—	8.2	—	125
	<i>Adaptive research trials, 1983-84</i>				
TPS2	4.2	16.6	7.4	27.6	123
IR20	3.6	—	5.8	—	123

^aMean of 1979-86.

Dominant dwarf mutants in rice induced with fractionated dose of gamma rays

C.R.A. Kumar, S.R. Sree Rangasamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

Presoaked seeds (24 h in distilled water) of TKM6 were exposed to gamma rays

of 35 kR in split or fractionated treatments with 4-h intervals between each exposure. The treatments were 0, 35 kR in a single dose, 30 + 5 kR, 25 + 10 kR, 20 + 15 kR, 15 + 20 kR, 10 + 25 kR, and 5 + 30 kR. In the first generation (M₁), plants survived from only 3 treatments: 5 + 30 kR (3 plants), 30 + 5 kR (5 plants), and 20 + 15 kR

Table 1. Performance of dominant dwarf mutants of TKM6 in the M₁. Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Yield/plant (g)
5 + 30 kR	84	11	22.9	6.2
30 + 5 kR	84	15	21.5	20.9
20 + 15 kR	85	17	20.9	19.6
Control	150	12	23.3	9.2

(5 plants). All plants were dwarf, irrespective of treatment (Table 1).

When the plants were forwarded to the M₂, the dwarf nature was

maintained, with increase in tiller number and per-plant yield (Table 2).

The dwarf plants were crossed with TKM6 in direct and reciprocal

combinations. The F₁ exhibited the dwarf nature (82.8 cm to 91.3 cm), confirming the dominant nature of the mutation. □

Table 2. Performance of dwarf mutants in M₂. Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Tillers (no.)			Panicle length (cm)			Yield/plant (g)		
	Mean ± SE	Range	CV	Mean ± SE	Range	CV	Mean ± SE	Range	CV	Mean ± SE	Range	CV
5 + 30 kR	80.00±1.33	71.5- 85.0	2.35	9.66±1.15	5-16	16.84	18.24±1.19	17.5-21.4	9.23	13.57±2.29	5.1-28.7	24.04
30 + 5 kR	79.66±0.56	75.5- 81.0	0.99	9.42±0.60	6-12	9.03	20.44±0.48	18.4-22.7	3.32	12.57±1.11	7.6-16.0	12.49
20 + 15 kR	80.11±1.16	75.0- 89.0	2.05	9.33±0.85	8-14	12.88	18.38±0.43	16.4-21.2	3.31	10.37±0.76	7.2-14.9	10.36
control	161.99±0.49	155.0-163.0	0.43	9.40±0.38	8-11	5.12	25.74±0.51	22.5-26.6	2.8	8.73±0.61	7.5-10.3	9.88

TNAU80030 - a promising medium-duration rice for Tamil Nadu

S. Palanisamy, G. A. Palanisamy, K. Natarajamoorthy, and R. Velusamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu 641003, India

We evaluated several breeding lines for yield potential and field tolerance for brown planthopper. IR13240-82-2-3-2, a derivative of IR30/ Babawee/ / IR36, was found most promising. It was designated TNAU80030 for testing at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, and was advanced to multilocation trial.

In 10 locations, TNAU80030 ranked first in four and tied with P837 in two

Yield of TNAU80030 in multilocation trials. Tamil Nadu, India, Sep-Oct 1985.

Location	Yield (t/ha)			
	TNAU80030	P837	CO 43	IR20
Aduthurai	4.4	3.9	3.3	3.3
Coimbatore	5.4	4.6	5.2	4.7
Tirur	4.7	4.4	3.2	4.5
Ambasamudram	5.2	5.0	4.7	4.9
Madurai	2.7	2.9	2.5	2.7
Pondicherry	6.4	8.9	6.9	5.8
Tirupathisaram	4.1	2.1	3.6	3.4
Trichy	3.8	4.5	6.6	3.7
Paiyur	5.2	5.1	4.3	4.7
Bhavanisagar	5.1	5.7	5.2	4.4
Mean	4.7	4.7	4.5	4.2

and with CO 43 in one location (see table). TNAU80030 has been advanced to adaptive research trials in farmers' fields.

TNAU80030 is semidwarf with a medium slender grain type and field tolerance for brown planthopper, blast, and rice tungro virus. □

IR18348-36-3-3, a promising rice for irrigated and slight acid sulfate soil in Vietnam

Nguyen Van Luat, Bui Ba Bong, and Pham Cong Voc, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute (CLRRI), Omon. Hau Giang, Vietnam

IR18348-36-3-3, a cross of IR5657-33-2-2 and IR2061-425-1-5-5, was selected at CLRRI from the International Rice Yield Nursery in early 1983. It has 100-115 d maturity, 95-110 cm height, and good grain quality, and is suitable for irrigated, slight acid sulfate soils.

Table 2. Reaction of IR18348-36-3-3 to insects and diseases at CLRRI.

Variety	Reaction ^a to			
	BPH	B1	BB	ShB
IR18348-36-3-3 (OM89)	3-5	4-5	5-7	7
NN6A	3	7-9	7	7
NN3A	3	7-9	7	7
Resistant check ^b	3	1	2	3
Susceptible check ^c	9	9	8	7

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice scale. ^b Resistant check was IR36 for brown planthopper (BPH), IR8 for blast (B1), Compo-selak for bacterial blight (BB), Tapochoz for sheath blight (ShB). ^c Susceptible check was TN1 for BPH, NN7A for B1, IR8 for BB, and IR36 for ShB.

Table 1. Yield of IR18348-36-3-3 in 1984-86 dry and wet seasons. Omon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Variety	Dry season			Wet season			Average
	1984	1985	1986	1983	1984	1985	
IR18348-36-3-3 (OM89)	5.5	5.4	5.4	6.1	5.6	5.3	5.5
NN3A (check)	4.4	5.5	5.3	4.8	5.7	4.3	4.9
NN6A (check)	4.8	5.3	5.2	5.2	5.6	5.5	5.2
cv (%)	24.5	-	20.4	13.3	-	26.8	1.3
LSD 5%	1.9		0.6	1.1		0.5	0.2